

IMPROVING MEASURES TO DETECT AND REDUCE THE EFFECTS OF VIBRATIONS CAUSED BY THE MOVEMENT OF VEHICLES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6589259>

Abdunazarov Akbarjon Shamsuddin o'g'li

Namangan Engineering and Civil Institute.

Annotation: *In the article car ways outgoing vibration population accommodation effect study, direction on spread speed and them reduce measures functional exit on measures see out.*

Keywords: *Car paths, vibration, building foundations, tunnels, bridges, reaction spectra.*

Population layer from kunga growth and of development car movement as a result on the roads yield to be vibrations roads near building and to buildings and to people negative effect shows. Vibration yield to be point of view in terms of cars movement as a result from the wheels yield to be vibrations variable pressure due to the surface is coming.

Vibrations effect seeker factors very much complex become including way coating unevenness, salinity and material, vehicle weight, speed and structure and dynamic properties of soil. Vibrations generated by the movement of cars are the object constructions and floors dynamics experimental measurement results again performance and analysis to do as a result in the car following laws set:

Soil type and especially his water with saturation degree hal seeker importance has Vibrations generated by highways are buildings and structures at the foundation located points shift spectra to nature effect. Rule as, to water saturated soil with spectra clear peak with tor diapazonga because it turns this without water with saturated ground high frequencies filters. All cases iron way movement as a result yield which was construction constructions vibrations, first and final stages in addition to is stationary.

Media commentary suggests that such transport in Western European countries Iron way and Car such as all engineering facilities (depo, workshops, tunnels, bridges and movement content) of the city old components to himself specific diversity sorry provocative architectural-historical inheritance a part as considered. This approach with, them y o q to do matter. From this in addition to them save stay and need when b o l, they are with depending on things y o q to do large sum they are spent noise and vibration.

On the ground and buildings near transport tools by vibrations create

According to local and foreign scientific and technical information and structures very much damage occurs and basically dynamics with ensuring the reliability of associated rolling stock, bridges, tunnels and overhead structures ways. Area where the highways pass supply to the necessity attention focused. How regulation hit current at the time simple requirements. That's it emphasis added we need basic attention noise, ecology and aimed at complying with sanitary norms.

This qualification at work out issues a part of the population points balanced development problems, their a part transportation oscillations with depending on problems. Practice that shows that current at this time the problem formed provocative individual tasks from each other separately see will be displayed and half is done. How a specialist general the problem or zigzag appropriate part of half does it yourself representation doing field for maximum benefit with instead increase aspires to, of this as a result, In this regard, in solving any highly specialized problem, first in turn, his general point of view in view how place occupy detection to the goal is compatible structure, and others with how cause and effect relationship with connected.

Population points create and development direction detection a lot in terms of completed data sheet availability, primarily man-made kind of possible which was dynamic loads, individual reactions are the elements of the complexes that make up a city and the consequences associated with them. Current at the time such problems optimization for good functional out mathematician methods available as, then dynamic actions, separately structures and their conglomerates behavior-all facts related to the actions available. For example economic aspects decisions analysis theory within even formal optimization even if it is not available.

Transport movement as a result in the soil to the surface coming physicist processes and in them located construction constructions reaction experimental and theoretically learn as a result a series scientific based on technician solutions taken. Integrated methodology, use construction industry and transport develop accelerate, cultural measures save statistics dynamics based on principled in terms of new technique functional was released soil and structures transport vibration.

Vibration levels of a number of buildings and from different types of transport their combinations, of this as a result his risk current regulations appropriate security supply for rated. In particular, this detected current at the time construction constructions transport vibration degree close available standards approaching, though and from them does not exceed both.

Floors and construction structures separately of the elements vibration amplitudes dangerous degree out remove for risks evaluation is given.

In the soil and being checked in buildings vibration currents spectral analysis was held and their o change soil conditions and structural structures with to be determined characteristic properties set.

Cars movement as a result vibrations properties learn for in the field test of vibration, vibration insulation measures apply through and vibration. The secret of insulation analysis to do for moving vehicle load foundations soil of the structure unifier model results that shows that moving from the car come ground vibrations low frequency mainly in the vertical y direction that is here base frequency 3 ~ 4 Gs diapazonida ground pulsation test mos is coming. Horizontal vibration to vertical vibration than dries much faster. Piles using vibration insulation for pile spacing, pile length and barrier width such as factors vibration. The secret to the insulation shows a significant mystery, the pile number of rows and pegs materials relatively makes little mystery. Optimized vibration insulation from the plan used without, moving from the car come outgoing vibration decrease by about 30 ~ 50% possible.

From the car low frequency of ground vibrations vibrations is superior. Soil vibrations basic frequency about 3 ~ 4 Gs This makes the ground pulsate test basic frequency.

Distance enlargement with vibration intensity decreases and X and Y in the direction of vibration Z in the direction of vibration than dries much faster.

Optimized vibration insulation from the plan used without, Cars movement as a result yield to be vibrations plot in the territory vibration decrease by about 30 ~ 50% possible.

USED PUBLICATIONS LIST:

1. Ильичев В. А., Юлдашев Ш. С., Саидов С. М. Исследование распространения вибрации при прохождении поездов в зависимости от расположения железнодорожного полотна // Основания, фундаменты и механика грунтов. – 1999. – №. 2. – С. 12-13.

2. Yuldashev S. S., Boytemirov M. Influence of the level of the location of the railway canvas on the propagation of waves from train motion // ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 05 (85). – 2020. – С. 140-143.

3. Yuldashev S. S., Karabaeva M. U. Soil surface vibrations in the training of metro trains in parallel tunnels // ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 05 (85). – 2020. – С. 117-121.

4. Mirsaidov M., Boytemirov M., Yuldashev F. Estimation of the Vibration Waves Level at Different Distances // Proceedings of FORM 2021. – Springer, Cham, 2022. – С. 207-215.

5. Исследование влияния сейсмоизоляции на динамические характеристики здания. А.СЮвмитов, С.Р Хакимов - 2020 - полито.уз

6. Бино ва иншоотларнинг сейсмик мустаҳкамлиги бўйича хорижий давлатлар (Россия, Япония, Хитой, АҚШ) меърий хужжатлари тахлили. С.Хакимов, Б.Шаропов, А.Абдуназаров -2022 sciencebox.uz 806-809-бет.

7. Юлдашев Ш. С., Саидов С. М., Набиев М. Я. Распространение вибраций в грунтах, возникающих при движении железнодорожных поездов //Молодой ученый. – 2015. – №. 11. – С. 481-483.

8. Юлдашев Ш. С., Саидов С. М., Набиев М. Я. Распространение вибраций в грунтах, возникающих при движении железнодорожных поездов //Молодой ученый. – 2015. – №. 11. – С. 481-483.

1. 10.Юлдашев Ш. С. и др. Влияние высоты расположения железнодорожного полотна на уровень колебания грунта, возникающего при движении поездов // Научное знание современности. – 2018. – №. 10. – С. 55-57.

2. 11. Юлдашев Ш. С., Карабаева М. У. Прогнозирование уровня вибрации в грунтах, распространяющейся от тоннелей метрополитена круглого сечения //Молодой ученый. – 2016. – №. 6. – С. 249-253.

3. 12. Influence of seismic isolation on the stress-strain state of buildings. A.S.Yuvmitov., S.R.Hakimov-Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in....2021-acta.polito.uz